

THE IMPACT OF LINGUISTIC CONSCIOUSNESS ON THE WORLD IMAGE

Linguistics

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Abstract

This article highlights the investigation of the world image, which is one of the fields of cognitive linguistics, which involves the concept of cognitive problems and their reflection in language, as a set of objective expressions that reflect the concentration of experience of a particular language community in language as a transmitter of certain ideas about the world. Moreover, language as a multifaceted phenomenon is explained and the language carrier's functions are determined. The indicators that constitute the essence of communicative competence are distinguished as, knowledge of language as a system (speech ability); have non-contradictory methods of communication (genre competence); and knowledge of the information space, the world (cognitive-epistemological competence).

The concept of “world landscape” is applied in psycholinguistics. A collection of concepts is a lexical phenomena that is unique to each speaking individual and each language community in the world. Similarities and differences in expressions in the world languages are being studied as a part of the research on the hypothesis of linguistic relativity.

The world's linguistic expression is the choice for how the world is structured through the prism of these words. “The artistic image of the world is also its reflection as a linguistic image. It appears in the mind of the reader when he reads a work (or in the mind of the spectator, the listener - when he perceives other works of art).

The image of the universe in an artistic text is created through language, while it reflects in the writer's mind an individual image of the world and is embodied in:

- in the choice of semantic elements of the work of art;
- in the choice of language tools: the use of groups of language units within a particular topic, increasing or decreasing the frequency of individual language units and their groups, individual - language units created by the author, etc .;
- in the individual use of means of artistic representation (system of tropes).

In the artistic depiction of the world, one can only find the concepts inherent in this author's perception of the world - the writer's individual views.” (Shahobiddinova Sh, 2016)

Linguistic units, which express the linguistic image of the world through works of art, are included in linguistics as “the sum of conceptual and procedural knowledge, through the perception of the owner of culture about real-world objects”. (Tarasov, 2000)

Works of art that are extremely valuable to some peoples, especially folklore specimens, are difficult to accept by other peoples.

There are also differences in the perception of simple cartoons. Uzbek audiences have a different approach to the content of cartoons such as “Bear and Masha” and “Tom and Jerry” than the people who created them. Respect for the elderly has a special place in the mentality of Uzbeks, and these carefree cartoons do not seem to be harmless to them at all.

J.N. Maslova describes the artistic image of the world as “a conceptual system that shapes the creative activity of the individual to create and interpret alternative poetic reality.” The content of the artistic description of the world includes encyclopedic knowledge, metapoetic knowledge and knowledge of language, in particular, artistic language. The main components of an artistic image combine artistic (poetic) concepts, perceptions of being, emotional experience, as well as ideas about artistic categories. (Maslova, 2011)

According to the Uzbek linguist N. Mahmudov: “Indeed, every nation has its own way of seeing, its own cognitive discipline, in general, its own principle of thinking. That is why the simple concepts of “national consciousness”, “national thinking”, “national feeling” have been giving power and coverage to the light in the heart of the human child for thousands of years. The essence and function of language are often interpreted in a very vague way. As if language is a social phenomenon that is the most important means of communication. The fact that language is a means of communication is just one of its many functions. In fact, language is, first of all, a means of seeing, hearing, knowing, perceiving the world. At the same time, we must not forget that language is a spiritual, aesthetic phenomenon.” (Mahmudov, 2012)

Cultural scientist and sociologist Yu.V. Rojdestvensky said that “the riches of the world's folklore - fairy tales, legends, proverbs and parables reflect the most ancient ideas about the world. Researchers of society and culture emphasize that myth is not only the basis of any work of art, but also the primary moral source of society: stories about gods and heroes should not only serve as role models and entertainment, but also teach simple rules of behavior in society ... there are ethical norms accepted by society. They are presented in authoritative texts: mythology, folklore, religious and scientific texts, works of art, such as the media.” (Rozhdestvensky Yu.V, 2009)

As a social being, a person may be in a state of communicative collaboration or communicative competition as long as he or she feels the need for daily speech exchange. Human cannot be free from the process of language, speech and communication.

Within the anthropocentric and discursive paradigms that define many areas of modern linguistics, scientists “do not work with abstract materialized devices or equipment, and they, like the researcher himself with this consciousness, engage in explicit speech activity.

In this regard, logically, the person “in the field of language - in communication, in the patterns of behavior formed in language, language unity” “Recognition” of the existence of languages and texts in the content is one of the most priority and main directions of linguistic research. (Kochetkova, 2006) Today, an independent field of linguistics has emerged - linguopersonology, which focuses on the study of a person's linguistic ability, speech and communicative competence.

The concept of person is one of the most controversial issues in linguistics. Scientists have developed many theories in this regard, each of which provides a unique definition of the concept.

However, despite the diversity of views on the nature of the individual, linguists agree that the essence of the concept is individuality and specificity, which characterizes the individual as a member of society or a particular community, becoming a system of socially significant features.

Linguists and psychologists have mastered a number of intellectual, cultural skills in speech; they unanimously agree that the customs, traditions, and values created by humanity are the result of the socialization of the individual. Through linguistic ability, a person is constantly evolving, focusing on realizing their potential in activity and communication.

The German scientist Leo Weisgerber, who studied the language carrier through the prism of the native language phenomenon, first put this problem forward.

In the works of V. Von Humboldt, G.I. Bogin, M.M. Bakhtin, the idea of the language carrier was put forward. For example, one of V. von Humboldt's antinomies contrasts individuality with language collectiveness. (Humboldt, 2001)

K. Fossler and his school of aesthetic idealism developed the ideas of this famous linguist. Its representatives studied the individual language and style of the writers that formed the basis of the study of idiolect. Of course, in this regard we must not forget the work of A.A. Potebnya.

Only F. de Saussure distinguished the concepts of language, speech, and speech activity. In his view, language and speech are contradictory in general and in particular because speech is individual and language is social. In addition, speech does not depend on physical external signs, but they, for example, acoustic aspects are inherent in speech. (Ariskina, 2011)

The first successful research on this topic in Russian linguistics was carried out in the book by V.V. Vinogradov “О языке художественной литературы” (“On the language of literary literature”). He distinguishes two options in the interpretation of the language carrier in the literary language - the identity of the author and the identity of the character. (Vinogradov, 1959)

The theoretical understanding of the phenomenon expressed by this phrase appeared in the 80s of the XX century, especially in the works of G.I. Bogin, who created a parametric model of individual differences and language carriers. The researcher considered the concept of language carrier to be the central concept of linguodidactics and understood it in terms of “a person who is ready to create and comprehend speech”. (Bogin, 2005)

In modern linguistics, there are different views and approaches to the analysis of the language carrier, which define the main component of this concept.

Many scholars argue that language carrier is a multidimensional concept, so all its components must be taken into account for its successful formation.

E.N. Barsukova considers the language carrier as a holistic concept: “a multidimensional, multilevel functional system that gives an idea of the ability of language and speech at the level of active and creative understanding of reality.” (Barsukova, 2007) Language as a multifaceted phenomenon is based on the principles of modern linguistics, in particular, the language carrier:

- systematic education, its components are high-level personal characteristics (emotional, communicative, mental, etc.) and other internal mental processes (thinking, memory);
- linguistic consciousness and speech play an important role in the development of the language carrier as the basic concepts of a successful communicative process;
- the language carrier has a social character;
- in the process of communication in a small group, the person fully understands his communicative powers;
- the language carrier is formed on the basis of linguistic and cultural relations, reflecting the peculiarities of man and his life, his relationship with the environment.

Hence, the main components of a language carrier are:

- values (value system);
- worldview (system of worldviews);
- culturological(level of culture mastery);
- personal;
- cognitive (understanding of lexico-phraseological possibilities of the native language, grammatical forms and constructions, methodological diversity);
- behavior (language etiquette, behavior in normal communication);
- speech skills;
- speech and intellectual ability;
- verbal feelings.

As a language carrier, we understand the following:

- highly developed person;
- a carrier of both the national language and universal culture;
- the one who has socio-cultural and speech resources;
- the one who can communicate freely in their native language and foreign languages in a multicultural space;
- the one who can make adequate use of the knowledge, speaking skills and abilities of different cultures acquired in the process of intercultural communication with different categories.

In this respect, the stratification of individuals has been cited in many cases. In our opinion, V. Karasik's contribution to the study of this issue is valuable. The scientist created a classification of an individual's linguistic activity based on the factor of linguocultural speech. (Karasik, 2016)

The category of linguist as an object of study found its place in the works of Yu. Karaulov, which served as a theoretical basis for further research in terms of linguistic personology. He proposed three levels of the hierarchical model of the language carrier:

- 1) verbal-semantic;
- 2) linguistic-cognitive;
- 3) pragmatic (motivational). (Karaulov, 2010)

The primary unit is the vocabulary of the individual, i.e. the words and phrases that a person uses in speech practice. The second corresponds to the intellectual, cognitive sphere, the characteristic unit of which is the concept of the individual's worldview and the category of the mechanism of consciousness, which expresses the specific features of this worldview. A tertiary unit is a communicative-activity need or motivation expressed through the interlocutor's intentions, which are determined by the communicative attitude.

The concept of language carrier is syncretic and interdisciplinary in nature. This category reveals its essence in an individual sense, which forms the individual thesaurus of the speaker, provides a basis for distinguishing specific types of speech process, defined by its unique state and specific parameters.

Following Y.N. Karaulov's views, we can describe the main features of the speech activity of strong, medium and weak language speakers and extroverts (ambitious), ambivert (flexible), introverts (human), and emphasize that the level of language does not depend on the psychological type of person and we can show that the language carrier is divided into nine types by lifestyle influences.

Y.N. Karaulov explained the content of the concept of language carrier, developed its structure and determined its level - verbal-semantic, linguistic-cognitive, pragmatic (motivational).

According to the scientist, a language carrier is a set of human abilities and characteristics that determine the creation and comprehension of speech works (texts), which differ in terms of structural and linguistic complexity as follows:

- a) the level of structural and linguistic complexity;
- b) the extent and accuracy of the reflection of reality;
- c) clear target direction.” (Karaulov, 2001)

The Russian scholar points out that the structure of the language carrier at each level consists of certain types of elements: units of a certain level, the relationship between their stereotypical associations is specific to each level of education.

In the process of learning the language carrier, we believe that communicative consciousness, communicative knowledge, skills and abilities, speech ability, communicative culture, and the image of taste are generalized.

Summarizing the views of modern researchers in the field of linguistics and linguodidactics, we use in our research the terms “language carrier” and “speaker” and distinguish them as follows:

1. A language carrier is a person who understands the world through “language points” (an object formed by the culture of speech), embedded in the conceptual system of language;
2. A speaker is a person who is expressive, appropriate, able to speak without overcoming communication barriers, and is able to achieve his / her goals.

The modern scientific paradigm implies a wide range of possibilities for the study of linguistic phenomena. Language is seen as a well-organized system of units and events at different levels that have a specific sound and grammatical structure. The results of this method of scientific study of linguistic phenomena are recorded in the dictionary and grammar of this or that language, which means the implementation of the structural principle. They also apply a functional principle in terms of their use in speech as they study language phenomena, and take into account the community of speakers who carry them out - the language carriers and the speakers.

At the current stage of scientific research, linguocentrism is being replaced by anthropocentrism, which studies language units not only as elements of a system, but also as a product of a national culture carrier. Anthropocentric tendencies have intensified interest in the role of language as a social phenomenon in the system of spiritual values of an ethnic group and in the communicant itself through its semiotic possibilities.

Man does not immediately become a person, he develops gradually, and many external factors are involved in this process. One of the leading positions among them belongs to the formation of the language carrier. In addition to the need to work, the need for communication and speech is also crucial in shaping a person. Language penetrates deep into the consciousness of man, and the external world, the laws of its observance, are true provides a lot of information.

Language carrier typology is one of the central problems of linguistics. For example, in traditional linguistics, it is an abstract and explicit kind of opposition. Speaking of the second direction, we are talking about the human idiolect as an object of study.

The typological stratification of the language carrier can be carried out according to sociolinguistics, linguoculturology, psycholinguistics and ethnolinguistics, as mentioned above. Accordingly, the identification of specific types of individuals is a criterion for determining the specific characteristics of these species - their manifestation in language under the influence of psychological, social, cultural or ethno-cultural factors. As every person uses this or that form of language, everyone manifests himself in a certain way.

Speech-specific forms of personality are at the same time an indicator of his social status, level of education, age and gender, individual psychological characteristics. Accordingly, the purpose of socio-cultural classification is to create verbal descriptions of representatives of a particular social circle.

Selecting the linguistic-cultural factor as the determining factor of the language carrier, V.I. Karasik emphasizes the linguocultural types – “the symbols familiar to the representatives of a particular culture, the commonality of situations is the culture of society.” (Karasik, 2016)

For example, the scientist selects certain types of Russians - intellectuals, merchants, officials, and so on, and considers them appropriate image models. While researchers classify the psychological differences of individuals, they are based on communicative behavior that is consistent with the human psychotype. At the same time, the focus in psychology is on the means of communication (classifications of Hippocrates, K.G. Jung, E. Fromm, and others) that are specific to a particular type of personality.

Research on the language carrier as a carrier of a particular language culture is widespread. For example, V.P.Neroznak defines two types of language carriers - standard and non-standard. The scholar refers to speakers who use an average level of literary language norms in a standard type of interaction. The non-standard type, on the other hand, includes people who show the highest level of speech culture or, conversely, the lowest level. (Neroznak, 1996)

According to Rustamov: “The national nature of communication with the being is the basis for the formation of ethnocultural thinking. Ethnocultural thinking, on the other hand, determines the characteristics of the national language.

Therefore, the interpretation of the national features of the understanding and perception of being has ethnocultural, political, moral, philosophical and linguistic significance.” (Rustamov, 2019)

The criterion for belonging to one or another type of language culture is "to bring one's linguistic consciousness closer to the ideal saturation of the richness of language in one form or another." (Karasik, 2016)

Such classification is carried out according to the requirements of the level of communicative competence. Scientists argue that it is advisable to use a rating scale that allows a native speaker (from the highest level to the lowest) to determine the level of competence, given its different manifestations in the choice of the level that defines a particular species.

It should be noted that communicative competence is a tool for measuring the level of formation of effective speech ability of a particular person, because its step-by-step nature allows to assess the level of competence (hereinafter - LC).

We distinguish the indicators that constitute the essence of communicative competence:

- 1) knowledge of language as a system (speech ability);
- 2) have non-contradictory methods of communication (genre competence);
- 3) knowledge of the information space, the world (cognitive - epistemological competence).

The above components of the level of competence are key elements of speech culture, since such selection and organization of language tools, adherence to language norms and rules of communication ethics allow to achieve high efficiency in performing communicative tasks in certain communication conditions.

According to the parameter “Level of LC formation”, we define strong, medium and weak language carrier.

Representatives of each of these species are to some extent carriers of speech culture. O.B. Sirotinina distinguishes speech culture within the framework of literary language into four types: upper class, middle literary, literary-speech and colloquial speech. The researcher considers the concept of strong, medium, and weak language carrier as categories that apply to a particular person in the process of speech formation. (Sirotinina, 2001)

The existence of an effective whole system of communication skills is the highest level of competence. LC is a method of communication that is the result of extensive experience in practical communicative activities provided by mass communication practices, given its suitability for communicative purposes. “Specificity in communication and conformity to ethical ideals” is characteristic of the speech of a strong linguist. In fact, “only a high-level speaker is distinguished by its unique style, strategy and tactics...” (Ivantsova, 2001)

It is with the uniqueness of the speech of a high-level speaker that another characteristic feature of high style - creativity - is also manifested. The communicative activity of a strong language bearer is consistent with the perception included in the concept of “good speech”. “Good speech” is characterized by the presence of such aspects as purposefulness, adherence to communication ethics, comprehensibility to the addressee, creativity. A distinctive feature of this type of speech is the ability to work with a large number of texts, which is one of the aspects that show the full intellectual development of a person.

The high-level language carrier on LC is distinguished by its maximum performance on all requirements. Such a level of speech can be achieved only in addition to the perfect study of language as a system, if a person is not satisfied with his level of knowledge and seeks to expand his intellectual potential. All this, in essence, belongs to a complex set of cognitive-psychological, behavioral, linguistic factors based on the activity of people, collective and pamphlet-like communication. (Kunin, 2001)

As a rule, the TV presenter is considered to be a high-level speaker, according to A.B. Sirotinina, although the TV presenter embodies the peculiarities of the Russian intellectual personality model, but compares it with the expression of “elastic morality”. (Sirotinina, 2007)

According to V.I. Karasik, those with high performance of LC - specialists – are:

- 1) “followers of language norms and laws” by their professional activity or natural speech sensitivity; or
- 2) authors of high-quality fiction, scientific, journalistic literature that create successful phrases that can be absorbed into the richness of the common vocabulary. (Karasik, 2004)

Note that there is no similarity between the concepts of “elite” and “elite speech” (“high-level speech”). Elite is a socially defined concept in terms of its dependence on a particular period of society’s existence. Elite speech is a phrase used only to describe perfect speech that meets the norms of literary language, so it cannot be a means of describing the speech of the people who make up the elite of society, as members of this class do not always show high LC in their speech.

In contrast to the high-level type of speech culture, the average literary level is characterized by a deviation from the level set as the criterion of maximum communication efficiency, and this category does not allow carriers to enter the above type.

Unlike a strong language learner, a medium language learner may not feel the need to supplement their knowledge. This type of culture carrier includes the part of the population with higher and secondary education that usually does not have the speech diversity skills inherent in functional types of speech.

It is characteristic for a medium language learner to have a conversational style and one of the functional styles required in the profession.

In the speech of such individuals, a deviation from the norms of orthological norms, i.e. speech culture, is often observed. As O.B. Sirotinina points out, “television and other media, as well as popular literature, often serve as unconditional and unqualified text for middle-class speakers, while middle-class literary-type speakers do not recognize such language-specific inaccuracies in texts.” (Sirotinina, 2007)

Weak language speakers are users of the oral literary or simple spoken type of speech culture. Such individuals use only their communication systems in any situation. Their speech is the opposite of elite speech in that it does not conform to “good” norms. In addition, slang, elements of vulgarism, and rude words, phrases are often used in the speech of representatives of this type of speech culture. Weak language speakers do not feel the need to supplement their knowledge, which in turn is reflected in LC indicators.

In addition to the above features, the language carrier also displays some features that do not have LC indicators. People’s speech will contain basic information about their personal characteristics. We are referring to certain forms of speech in which a psychological portrait of the individual is manifested. The peculiarity of communicative activity is to determine which attitude prevails and the most effective means of determining the vector of individual activity.

One of the authoritative methods of measuring personality traits is stratification based on this extraversion or introversion attitude. The distinction between extrovert and introvert individuals was put forward by K.G. Jung. According to his teachings, the thoughts and feelings of introverts are focused on a specific “I” and are closely related to it. All forms of reflection of the human inner world are stimuli of introvert activity. Distinguishing by an extroverted attitude individuals focus on the outside world, the people and situations around them. Each species is characterized by distinctive behavioral traits, and the individual is correspondingly unique to the species. (Jung, 2006)

American psychologists associate extroversion in the context of social behavior with understanding. Introversion is seen as a “tendency to avoid social contact.” (Hyell, 2008)

A distinctive feature of the extrovert is the need for communication. This feature of theirs certainly does not mean that their speech corresponds to a high level of LC, as the communicator may consider it “empty”.

Since it is impossible for one of the groups to exist in pure form, the concept of “ambivert” in psychology serves as a kind that combines the characteristics of an extrovert and an introvert. This syncretic psychotype is the most common phenomenon among humans.

Thus, taking into account the LC scale and internal psychological dimensions, the following types of language carrier are identified:

- 1) strong language carrier - introvert; strong language carrier - ambivert; strong language carrier - extrovert;
- 2) average language carrier - introvert; average language carrier - ambivert; average language carrier - extrovert;
- 3) weak language carrier - introvert; weak language carrier - ambivert; weak language carrier - extrovert.

In general, these features determine the behavior of the language carrier.

We emphasize that the level of competence is independent of internal measurements, as individuals in extraversion and introversion relationships may also exhibit the highest and lowest scores of LC. Recall that the decisive factor for the level of LC is the factor of intellectual development, which is not related to the measurement of human temperament. LC is an indicator of intellectual development, experience of spiritual and practical activity.

Relation to a particular psychotype is determined both genetically and socially. Therefore, these two aspects of the speaker are not related to each other. However, they can be observed and influenced in some way in the language carrier, in the person’s behavior.

We can observe the level of choice in relation to means of communication in both verbal and nonverbal communication of extroverts, ambiverts and introverts. Because extroverts design their activities, it is clear that they are more likely to resort to nonverbal means of communication (gestures, facial expressions, etc.) than introverts are.

We can observe the manifestation of each psychotype at the following level:

- phonetic (speed of speech, tone, intonational features of words, etc.);
- lexical (the importance of national formal words in the speech of extroverts);
- syntactic (use of motivational structures, etc.).

It has also been observed that extroverts and introverts have different emotional-evaluation criteria for the same stimulus words. Scientists have determined this through experiments. A more positive relationship was noted between the extroverts' responses. Introverts have often reacted negatively to words of encouragement. This is manifested by their tendency to express indifference in negative evaluation. (Hyell, 2008)

Thus, everyone has a need for communication, but individuals who can be called extroverts or introverts meet this need in different ways. Extroverts predetermine the interdependence of content and expression in their speech activities. But introverts tend to focus on words that express their 'I' because they tend to reflect inner emotion, which gives us the right to think about the level of development that applies to inner speech. Obviously, extroverts have better verbal ability than introverts, but this does not mean that they have a high level of LC, as this is provided through the mental development of the individual.

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